

Supplementary material for “*Revisiting the size effect in software fault prediction models*”

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1 Kernel Density plots of faults in all systems

Figure 1: Kernel Density plot for faults in Eclipse JDT

N = 1862 Bandwidth = 0.2193

Figure 2: Kernel Density plot for faults in Eclipse Mylyn

Figure 3: Kernel Density plot for faults in Eclipse PDE

Figure 4: Kernel Density plot for faults in Eclipse Equinox

Figure 5: Kernel Density plot for faults in Apache Lucene (2.4)

Figure 6: Kernel Density plot for faults in Apache Ant

Figure 7: Kernel Density plot for faults in Apache Ivy

Figure 8: Kernel Density plot for faults in jEdit

Figure 9: Kernel Density plot for faults in Apache Log4J

Figure 10: Kernel Density plot for faults in Apache Lucene (2.2)

Figure 11: Kernel Density plot for faults in Apache POI

Figure 12: Kernel Density plot for faults in Apache Prop

Figure 13: Kernel Density plot for faults in Apache Synapse

Figure 14: Kernel Density plot for faults in Apache Tomcat

Figure 15: Kernel Density plot for faults in Apache Velocity

Figure 16: Kernel Density plot for faults in Apache Xalan

Figure 17: Kernel Density plot for faults in Apache Xerces

2 Mediation and moderation analysis SPSS Scripts

```

1 PROCESS
2   y=faults
3   /x=rfc
4   /m=loc
5   /total=1
6   /decimals=F10.4
7   /effsize=1
8   /boot=5000
9   /conf=95
10  /model=4.
11 PROCESS
12  y=faults
13  /x=wmc
14  /m=loc
15  /total=1
16  /decimals=F10.4
17  /effsize=1
18  /boot=5000
19  /conf=95

```

```

20 /model=4.
21 PROCESS
22   y=faults
23   /x=cbo
24   /m=loc
25   /total=1
26   /decimals=F10.4
27   /effsize=1
28   /boot=5000
29   /conf=95
30   /model=4.
31 PROCESS
32   y=faults
33   /x=dit
34   /m=loc
35   /total=1
36   /decimals=F10.4
37   /effsize=1
38   /boot=5000
39   /conf=95
40   /model=4.
41 PROCESS
42   y=faults
43   /x=lcom
44   /m=loc
45   /total=1
46   /decimals=F10.4
47   /effsize=1
48   /boot=5000
49   /conf=95
50   /model=4.
51 PROCESS
52   y=faults
53   /x=fanIn
54   /m=loc
55   /total=1
56   /decimals=F10.4
57   /effsize=1
58   /boot=5000
59   /conf=95
60   /model=4.
61 PROCESS
62   y=faults
63   /x=fanOut
64   /m=loc
65   /total=1
66   /decimals=F10.4
67   /effsize=1
68   /boot=5000
69   /conf=95
70   /model=4.

```

Listing 1: Mediation analysis SPSS Script

```

1 PROCESS
2   y=totalbugs
3   /x=rfc
4   /w=loc

```

```

5 /plot=1
6 /covcoeff=1
7 /decimals=F12.6
8 /jn=1
9 /modelbt=1
10 /boot=5000
11 /conf=95
12 /model=1.
13
14 PROCESS
15 y=totalbugs
16 /x=wmc
17 /w=loc
18 /plot=1
19 /covcoeff=1
20 /decimals=F12.6
21 /jn=1
22 /modelbt=1
23 /boot=5000
24 /conf=95
25 /model=1.
26
27 PROCESS
28 y=totalbugs
29 /x=cbo
30 /w=loc
31 /plot=1
32 /covcoeff=1
33 /decimals=F12.6
34 /jn=1
35 /modelbt=1
36 /boot=5000
37 /conf=95
38 /model=1.
39
40 PROCESS
41 y=totalbugs
42 /x=dit
43 /w=loc
44 /plot=1
45 /covcoeff=1
46 /decimals=F12.6
47 /jn=1
48 /modelbt=1
49 /boot=5000
50 /conf=95
51 /model=1.
52
53 PROCESS
54 y=totalbugs
55 /x=lcom
56 /w=loc
57 /plot=1
58 /covcoeff=1
59 /decimals=F12.6
60 /jn=1
61 /modelbt=1

```

```

62 /boot=5000
63 /conf=95
64 /model=1.
65
66 PROCESS
67 y=totalbugs
68 /x=fanIn
69 /w=loc
70 /plot=1
71 /covcoeff=1
72 /decimals=F12.6
73 /jn=1
74 /modelbt=1
75 /boot=5000
76 /conf=95
77 /model=1.
78
79 PROCESS
80 y=totalbugs
81 /x=fanOut
82 /w=loc
83 /plot=1
84 /covcoeff=1
85 /decimals=F12.6
86 /jn=1
87 /modelbt=1
88 /boot=5000
89 /conf=95
90 /model=1.

```

Listing 2: Moderation analysis SPSS Script

3 Mediation analysis results for all individual systems

Table 1: Regression and mediation analysis results for Eclipse JDT Core

Metrics	B (Total Effect)	R2	F	P	SE(B)	95% CI		Direct Effect (c')	Indirect Effect (ab)	BootCILL	BootCIUL	Sig mediation effect
						LL	UL					
RFC	.0040	.3223	466.010	.00	.0002	.0037	.0044	.0016	.0024	-.0009	.0043	X
WMC	.0054	.3249	471.614	.00	.0002	.0049	.0059	.0014	.0040	-.0038	.0079	X
CBO	.0352	.2376	305.341	.00	.0020	.0312	.0391	.0160	.0191	.0118	.0279	✓
LCOM	.0001	.1104	121.645	.00	.0000	.0001	.0002	.0000	.0001	.0001	.0004	X
Fan-in	.0324	.1198	133.381	.00	.0028	.0269	.0379	.0134	.0190	.0100	.0310	✓
Fan-out	.0653	.2404	310.149	.00	.0037	.0580	.0725	.0288	.0364	.0200	.0552	✓

Table 2: Regression and mediation analysis results for Eclipse Mylyn

Metrics	B (Total Effect)	R2	F	P	SE(B)	95% CI		Direct Effect (c')	Indirect Effect (ab)	BootCILL	BootCIUL	Sig. mediation effect
						LL	UL					
RFC	.0049	.0900	180.104	.00	.0004	.0042	.0056	.0081	-.0032	-.0032	.0063	X
WMC	.0084	.0535	102.958	.00	.0008	.0067	.0100	.0098	-.0014	-.0097	.0235	X
CBO	.0169	.0551	106.084	.00	.0016	.0137	.0201	.0140	.0029	.0009	.0134	✓
LCOM	.0007	.0320	60.182	.00	.0001	.0005	.0008	.0002	.0004	-.0003	.0014	X
Fan-in	.0092	.0114	21.014	.00	.0020	.0052	.0131	.0071	.0021	.0006	.0098	✓
Fan-out	.0683	.1505	322.405	.00	.0038	.0609	.0758	.0658	.0026	-.0014	.0269	✓

Table 3: Regression and mediation analysis results for Eclipse PDE

Metrics	B (Total Effect)	R2	F	P	SE(B)	95% CI		Direct Effect (c')	Indirect Effect (ab)	BootCILL	BootCIUL	Sig. mediation effect
						LL	UL					
RFC	.0046	.1260	214.290	.00	.0003	.0039	.0052	.0048	-.0003	-.0055	.0052	X
WMC	.0084	.1060	176.168	.00	.0006	.0072	.0096	.0011	.0073	-.0002	.0149	X
CBO	.0118	.0466	72.560	.00	.0014	.0091	.0145	.0036	.0082	.0036	.0189	✓
LCOM	.0009	.0604	95.572	.00	.0001	.0008	.0011	-.0002	.0011	.0006	.0020	X
Fan-in	.0060	.0090	13.529	.00	.0016	.0028	.0092	.0033	.0027	.0011	.0081	✓
Fan-out	.0333	.0871	141.758	.00	.0028	.0278	.0388	.0072	.0261	.0104	.0438	X

Table 4: Regression and mediation analysis results for Eclipse Equinox

Metrics	B (Total Effect)	R2	F	P	SE(B)	95% CI		Direct Effect (c')	Indirect Effect (ab)	BootCILL	BootCIUL	Sig. mediation effect
						LL	UL					
RFC	.0073	.3264	134.2169	.00	.0006	.0061	.0086	-.0084	.0158	.0074	.0262	✓
WMC	.0148	.3671	160.6732	.00	.0012	.0125	.0171	-.0046	.0194	-.0117	.0448	X
CBO	.0954	.4797	255.4097	.00	.0060	.0837	.1072	.0697	.0257	.0091	.0488	✓
LCOM	.0026	.3926	179.0405	.00	.0002	.0022	.0029	.0013	.0012	-.0001	.0026	X
Fan-in	.1315	.1776	59.8006	.00	.0170	.0980	.1650	.0894	.0422	.0163	.0868	✓
Fan-out	.1025	.4242	204.0981	.00	.0072	.0884	.1167	.0630	.0395	.0127	.0766	✓

Table 5: Regression and mediation analysis results for Eclipse Lucene (2.4)

Metrics	B (Total Effect)	R2	F	P	SE(B)	95% CI		Direct Effect (c')	Indirect Effect (ab)	BootCILL	BootCIUL	Sig. mediation effect
						LL	UL					
RFC	.0073	.3264	134.216	.00	.0006	.0061	.0086	-.0084	.0158	.0071	.0263	✓
WMC	.0148	.3671	160.673	.00	.0012	.0125	.0171	-.0046	.0194	-.0137	.0446	X
CBO	.0954	.4797	255.410	.00	.0060	.0837	.1072	.0697	.0257	.0085	.0485	✓
LCOM	.0026	.3926	179.041	.00	.0002	.0022	.0029	.0013	.0012	.0000	.0027	✓
Fan-in	.1315	.1776	59.801	.00	.0170	.0980	.1650	.0894	.0422	.0154	.0890	✓
Fan-out	.1025	.4242	204.098	.00	.0072	.0884	.1167	.0630	.0395	.0130	.0768	✓

Table 6: Regression and mediation analysis results for Apache Ant

Metrics	B (Total Effect)	R2	F	P	SE(B)	95% CI		Direct Effect (c')	Indirect Effect (ab)	BootCILL	BootCIUL	Sig. mediation effect
						LL	UL					
RFC	.0209	.4252	528.1630	.00	.0009	.0191	.0227	.0120	.0090	.0028	.0132	✓
WMC	.0537	.3117	323.3213	.00	.0030	.0478	.0596	.0142	.0395	.0265	.0577	✓
CBO	.0117	.0731	56.2970	.00	.0016	.0086	.0147	.0046	.0071	.0024	.0211	✓
LCOM	.0016	.2485	236.0904	.00	.0001	.0014	.0018	.0006	.0010	.0006	.0023	✓
Fan-in	.0080	.0328	24.2104	.00	.0016	.0048	.0112	.0035	.0045	.0006	.0123	✓
Fan-out	.1051	.2662	259.0128	.00	.0065	.0922	.1179	.0410	.0640	.0444	.0890	✓

Table 7: Regression and mediation analysis results for Apache Ivy

Metrics	B (Total Effect)	R2	F	P	SE(B)	95% CI		Direct Effect (c')	Indirect Effect (ab)	BootCILL	BootCIUL	Sig. mediation effect
						LL	UL					
RFC	.0057	.2559	114.5076	.00	.0005	.0047	.0068	.0014	.0043	-.0003	.0112	X
WMC	.0135	.1648	65.7267	.00	.0017	.0102	.0167	.0003	.0131	.0061	.0215	X
CBO	.0091	.0906	33.1603	.00	.0016	.0060	.0122	.0018	.0072	.0031	.0140	X
LCOM	.0002	.0491	17.2006	.00	.0000	.0001	.0002	-.0001	.0002	.0001	.0006	✓
Fan-in	.0025	.0047	1.5742	.21	.0020	-.0014	.0063	.0008	.0017	-.0008	.0054	X
Fan-out	.0253	.2057	86.2396	.00	.0027	.0200	.0307	.0089	.0165	.0073	.0276	✓

Table 8: Regression and mediation analysis results for jEdit

Metrics	B (Total Effect)	R2	F	P	SE(B)	95% CI		Direct Effect (c')	Indirect Effect (ab)	BootCILL	BootCIUL	Sig. mediation effect
						LL	UL					
RFC	.0006	.0354	17.4455	.00	.0001	.0003	.0008	.0010	-.0005	-.0013	.0001	X
WMC	.0008	.0135	6.4841	.01	.0003	.0002	.0014	.0015	-.0007	-.0026	.0006	X
CBO	.0012	.0304	14.8769	.00	.0003	.0006	.0018	.0011	.0000	-.0002	.0006	X
LCOM	.0000	.0020	.9330	.33	.0000	.0000	.0000	.0000	.0000	.0000	.0000	X
Fan-in	.0012	.0246	11.9791	.00	.0003	.0005	.0019	.0011	.0001	-.0001	.0006	X
Fan-out	.0036	.0369	18.1952	.00	.0008	.0019	.0052	.0040	-.0004	-.0021	.0017	X

Table 9: Regression and mediation analysis results for Log4J

Metrics	B (Total Effect)	R2	F	P	SE(B)	95% CI		Direct Effect (c')	Indirect Effect (ab)	BootCILL	BootCIUL	Sig. mediation effect
						LL	UL					
RFC	.0111	.0424	8.7302	.00	.0038	.0037	.0185	-.0188	.0299	-.0005	.0572	X
WMC	.0385	.0594	12.4507	.00	.0109	.0170	.0601	.0097	.0288	-.0163	.0714	X
CBO	.0464	.0857	18.4653	.00	.0108	.0251	.0676	.0330	.0134	-.0063	.0349	X
LCOM	.0002	.0020	.3932	.53	.0003	-.0004	.0008	-.0013	.0015	.0007	.0062	X
Fan-in	.0381	.0465	9.6052	.00	.0123	.0139	.0624	.0253	.0128	-.0004	.0268	X
Fan-out	.0663	.0428	8.8186	.00	.0223	.0223	.1103	-.0126	.0788	.0089	.1538	X

Table 10: Regression and mediation analysis results for Apache Lucene (2.2)

Metrics	B (Total Effect)	R2	F	P	SE(B)	95% CI		Direct Effect (c')	Indirect Effect (ab)	BootCILL	BootCIUL	Sig. mediation effect
						LL	UL					
RFC	.0678	.5379	391.0771	.00	.0034	.0611	.0746	.0845	-.0167	-.0459	-.0006	✓
WMC	.1549	.4891	321.6820	.00	.0086	.1379	.1719	.1707	-.0158	-.0557	.0262	X
CBO	.1180	.2327	101.8802	.00	.0117	.0950	.1410	.0869	.0312	.0043	.0862	✓
LCOM	.0044	.4284	251.8718	.00	.0003	.0038	.0049	.0037	.0007	.0000	.0023	✓
Fan-in	.0765	.0775	28.2219	.00	.0144	.0482	.1049	.0706	.0059	-.0048	.0283	X
Fan-out	.2680	.3069	148.7756	.00	.0220	.2247	.3112	.1692	.0987	-.0010	.2227	X

Table 11: Regression and mediation analysis results for Apache POI

Metrics	B (Total Effect)	R2	F	P	SE(B)	95% CI		Direct Effect (c')	Indirect Effect (ab)	BootCILL	BootCIUL	Sig. mediation effect
						LL	UL					
RFC	.0359	.4670	375.8429	.00	.0019	.0323	.0396	.0376	-.0016	-.0181	.0011	X
WMC	.0694	.2718	160.1124	.00	.0055	.0586	.0801	.0608	.0085	.0013	.0641	✓
CBO	.0306	.0956	45.3230	.00	.0045	.0216	.0395	.0243	.0063	.0010	.0313	✓
LCOM	.0017	.1424	71.2203	.00	.0002	.0013	.0020	.0012	.0004	.0001	.0024	✓
Fan-in	.0135	.0150	6.5311	.01	.0053	.0031	.0238	.0110	.0025	-.0002	.0179	X
Fan-out	.0929	.1882	99.4784	.00	.0093	.0746	.1112	.0752	.0177	.0037	.0774	✓

Table 12: Regression and mediation analysis results for Apache Prop

Metrics	B (Total Effect)	R2	F	P	SE(B)	95% CI		Direct Effect (c')	Indirect Effect (ab)	BootCILL	BootCIUL	Sig. mediation effect
						LL	UL					
RFC	.0037	.0422	28.2549	.00	.0007	.0023	.0050	.0023	.0013	-.0022	.0054	X
WMC	.0088	.0280	18.4692	.00	.0021	.0048	.0128	.0037	.0051	.0015	.0090	X
CBO	.0067	.0221	14.5381	.00	.0017	.0032	.0101	.0024	.0042	.0017	.0073	X
LCOM	.0007	.0247	16.2888	.00	.0002	.0004	.0011	.0004	.0004	.0002	.0006	X
Fan-in	.0019	.0014	.8722	.35	.0021	-.0021	.0060	.0011	.0008	.0000	.0019	X
Fan-out	.0095	.0276	18.2281	.00	.0022	.0052	.0139	.0038	.0058	.0019	.0102	X

Table 15: Regression and mediation analysis results for Apache Velocity

Metrics	B (Total Effect)	R2	F	P	SE(B)	95% CI		Direct Effect (c')	Indirect Effect (ab)	BootCILL	BootCIUL	Sig. mediation effect
						LL	UL					
RFC	.0336	.2670	78.3029	.00	.0038	.0261	.0411	.0197	.0139	.0078	.0400	✓
WMC	.0587	.2215	61.1887	.00	.0075	.0439	.0735	.0219	.0369	.0210	.0869	✓
CBO	.0391	.0734	17.0318	.00	.0095	.0204	.0578	.0259	.0132	-.0018	.0477	X
LCOM	.0014	.1856	49.0021	.00	.0002	.0010	.0017	.0006	.0007	.0004	.0040	✓
Fan-in	.0135	.0065	1.4086	.24	.0114	-.0089	.0359	.0039	.0096	-.0074	.0545	X
Fan-out	.1064	.2135	58.3786	.00	.0139	.0789	.1338	.0750	.0314	.0031	.0725	✓

Table 16: Regression and mediation analysis results for Apache Xalan

Metrics	B (Total Effect)	R2	F	P	SE(B)	95% CI		Direct Effect (c')	Indirect Effect (ab)	BootCILL	BootCIUL	Sig. mediation effect
						LL	UL					
RFC	.0063	.1047	103.3359	.00	.0006	.0051	.0076	.0039	.0024	.0018	.0033	✓
WMC	.0107	.0566	52.9984	.00	.0015	.0078	.0136	.0055	.0052	.0035	.0075	✓
CBO	.0082	.0396	36.4578	.00	.0014	.0055	.0109	.0069	.0013	.0001	.0028	✓
LCOM	.0002	.0367	33.6599	.00	.0000	.0002	.0003	.0001	.0001	.0001	.0002	✓
Fan-in	.0059	.0146	13.0696	.00	.0016	.0027	.0091	.0054	.0005	-.0007	.0020	X
Fan-out	.0180	.0490	45.5226	.00	.0027	.0127	.0232	.0139	.0040	.0014	.0072	✓

Table 13: Regression and mediation analysis results for Apache Synapse

Metrics	B (Total Effect)	R2	F	P	SE(B)	95% CI		Direct Effect (c')	Indirect Effect (ab)	BootCILL	BootCIUL	Sig. mediation effect
						LL	UL					
RFC	.0202	.2284	72.2448	.00	.0024	.0155	.0249	.0195	.0007	-.0119	.0134	X
WMC	.0304	.0659	17.2140	.00	.0073	.0160	.0448	-.0023	.0326	.0166	.0576	X
CBO	.0284	.0950	25.6104	.00	.0056	.0174	.0395	.0165	.0120	.0042	.0240	✓
LCOM	.0009	.0225	5.6073	.02	.0004	.0002	.0017	-.0002	.0011	.0003	.0026	X
Fan-in	.0081	.0059	1.4546	.23	.0067	-.0051	.0214	.0085	-.0004	-.0043	.0106	X
Fan-out	.0681	.1816	54.1450	.00	.0093	.0499	.0864	.0403	.0278	.0127	.0500	✓

Table 14: Regression and mediation analysis results for Apache Tomcat

Metrics	B (Total Effect)	R2	F	P	SE(B)	95% CI		Direct Effect (c')	Indirect Effect (ab)	BootCILL	BootCIUL	Sig. mediation effect
						LL	UL					
RFC	.0052	.2017	209.6857	.00	.0004	.0045	.0059	.0035	.0017	.0000	.0039	✓
WMC	.0082	.0880	80.1299	.00	.0009	.0064	.0100	-.0002	.0085	.0046	.0130	X
CBO	.0139	.0887	80.7797	.00	.0015	.0108	.0169	.0056	.0083	.0042	.0135	✓
LCOM	.0001	.0319	27.3922	.00	.0000	.0000	.0001	.0000	.0001	.0001	.0002	X
Fan-in	.0069	.0141	11.8949	.00	.0020	.0030	.0109	.0036	.0034	.0011	.0070	✓
Fan-out	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	N/A

Table 17: Regression and mediation analysis results for Apache Xerces

Metrics	B (Total Effect)	R2	F	P	SE(B)	95% CI		Direct Effect (c')	Indirect Effect (ab)	BootCILL	BootCIUL	Sig. mediation effect
						LL	UL					
RFC	.1407	.4824	546.109	.00	.0060	.1288	.1525	.1449	-.0043	-.0362	.0404	X
WMC	.2118	.2005	146.967	.00	.0175	.1775	.2461	.0794	.1323	.0670	.2328	✓
CBO	.2889	.2543	199.878	.00	.0204	.2488	.3291	.1786	.1103	.0624	.1810	✓
LCOM	.0083	.1145	75.742	.00	.0010	.0064	.0101	.0021	.0062	.0029	.0129	✓
Fan-in	.1560	.0459	28.2062	.00	.0294	.0983	.2136	.0824	.0736	.0378	.1371	✓
Fan-out	.6546	.4615	502.193	.00	.0292	.5972	.7119	.5370	.1176	.0261	.2374	✓

4 Mediation analysis results for aggregated data

Results from the DAMB dataset are shown in Table 18, results from the JURE dataset are shown in Table 19.

Table 18: Regression and mediation analysis results for DAMB dataset

Metrics	B (Total effect)	R^2	F	P	SE(B)	95% CI		Direct Effect (c')	Indirect Effect (ab)	BootCILL	BootCIUL	Sig mediation effect
						LL	UL					
RFC	0.005	0.190	1235.18	0.000	0.00	0.004	0.005	0.004	0.000	-0.002	0.002	X
WMC	0.006	0.160	964.33	0.000	0.000	0.006	0.006	0.003	0.003	-0.002	0.005	X
CBO	0.022	0.10	605.04	0.00	0.001	0.020	0.024	0.013	0.009	0.005	0.013	✓
DIT	-0.032	0.002	8.45	0.000	0.009	-0.053	-0.010	-0.032	-0.000	-0.006	0.006	X
LCOM	0.000	0.050	270.67	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	✓
Fan-in	0.014	0.03	162.63	0.00	0.015	0.012	0.017	0.008	0.006	0.003	0.012	✓
Fan-out	0.060	0.180	1134.24	0.000	0.002	0.057	0.064	0.042	0.019	0.010	0.028	✓

Table 19: Regression and mediation analysis results for JURE dataset

Metrics	B (Total effect)	R^2	F	P	SE(B)	95% CI		Direct Effect (c')	Indirect Effect (ab)	BootCILL	BootCIUL	Sig mediation effect
						LL	UL					
RFC	0.013	0.058	344.39	0.00	0.035	0.005	0.011	0.006	0.008	0.005	0.011	✓
WMC	0.027	0.037	214.50	0.00	0.002	0.016	0.031	0.004	0.022	0.016	0.031	✓
CBO	0.017	0.019	106.57	0.00	0.002	0.006	0.013	0.008	0.009	0.006	0.013	✓
DIT	0.044	0.001	4.34	0.00	0.021	-0.009	0.012	0.043	0.002	-0.009	0.012	X
LCOM	0.000	0.005	25.95	0.00	0.000	0.000	0.001	-0.000	0.000	0.003	0.001	✓
Fan-in	0.014	0.004	20.77	0.000	0.002	0.003	0.009	0.003	0.005	0.003	0.009	✓
Fan-out	0.060	0.058	346.27	0.00	0.004	0.003	0.015	0.047	0.020	0.003	0.015	✓

5 Moderation analysis results for all individual systems

Table 20: Moderation effect of size on the relationship between individual OO metrics and Faults in Eclipse JDT

	Interaction Effect (P)	LOC	Effect	P	LLCI	ULCI
RFC	0.00	Low	0.0025	0.00	0.0016	0.0033
		Med	0.0024	0.00	0.0016	0.0033
		High	0.0024	0.00	0.0015	0.0032
WMC	0.00	Low	0.0014	0.08	-0.0002	0.0031
		Med	0.0014	0.09	-0.0002	0.0030
		High	0.0011	0.17	-0.0005	0.0028
CBO	0.14	Low	NA	NA	NA	NA
		Med	NA	NA	NA	NA
		High	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCOM	0.32	Low	NA	NA	NA	NA
		Med	NA	NA	NA	NA
		High	NA	NA	NA	NA
Fan-in	0.02	Low	0.0096	0.00	0.0036	0.0156
		Med	0.0098	0.00	0.0039	0.0157
		High	0.0106	0.00	0.0050	0.0162
Fan-out	0.02	Low	0.0316	0.00	0.0230	0.0403
		Med	0.0313	0.00	0.0227	0.0398
		High	0.0298	0.00	0.0214	0.0382

Table 21: Moderation effect of size on the relationship between individual OO metrics and Faults in Eclipse PDE

	Interaction Effect (P)	LOC	Effect	P	LLCI	ULCI
RFC	0.27	Low	NA	NA	NA	NA
		Med	NA	NA	NA	NA
		High	NA	NA	NA	NA
WMC	0.84	Low	NA	NA	NA	NA
		Med	NA	NA	NA	NA
		High	NA	NA	NA	NA
CBO	0.63	Low	NA	NA	NA	NA
		Med	NA	NA	NA	NA
		High	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCOM	0.00	Low	-0.0009	0.00	-0.0013	-0.0004
		Med	-0.0008	0.00	-0.0013	-0.0004
		High	-0.0007	0.00	-0.0011	-0.0003
Fan-in	0.58	Low	NA	NA	NA	NA
		Med	NA	NA	NA	NA
		High	NA	NA	NA	NA
Fan-out	0.99	Low	NA	NA	NA	NA
		Med	NA	NA	NA	NA
		High	NA	NA	NA	NA

Table 22: Moderation effect of size on the relationship between individual OO metrics and Faults in Eclipse Mylyn

	Interaction Effect (P)	LOC	Effect	P	LLCI	ULCI
RFC	0.00	Low	0.0044	0.00	0.0027	0.0061
		Med	0.0043	0.00	0.0026	0.0061
		High	0.0042	0.00	0.0024	0.0059
WMC	0.00	Low	-0.0013	0.54	-0.0053	0.0028
		Med	-0.0014	0.50	-0.0055	0.0027
		High	-0.0018	0.38	-0.0059	0.0023
CBO	0.00	Low	0.0056	0.01	0.0013	0.0099
		Med	0.0064	0.00	0.0022	0.0105
		High	0.0088	0.00	0.0051	0.0125
LCOM	0.00	Low	0.0005	0.00	0.0002	0.0007
		Med	0.0005	0.00	0.0002	0.0007
		High	0.0004	0.00	0.0002	0.0007
Fan-in	0.00	Low	-0.0039	0.15	-0.0091	0.0014
		Med	-0.0026	0.31	-0.0076	0.0024
		High	0.0011	0.60	-0.0032	0.0055
Fan-out	0.00	Low	0.0563	0.00	0.0462	0.0664
		Med	0.0571	0.00	0.0472	0.0669
		High	0.0592	0.00	0.0500	0.0685

Table 23: Moderation effect of size on the relationship between individual OO metrics and Faults in Eclipse Equinox

	Interaction Effect (P)	LOC	Effect	P	LLCI	ULCI
RFC	0.00	Low	-0.0042	0.10	-0.0092	0.0008
		Med	-0.0044	0.08	-0.0093	0.0005
		High	-0.0050	0.04	-0.0098	-0.0002
WMC	0.00	Low	0.0022	0.65	-0.0073	0.0118
		Med	0.0017	0.72	-0.0078	0.0112
		High	0.0003	0.95	-0.0090	0.0096
CBO	0.00	Low	0.0595	0.00	0.0404	0.0785
		Med	0.0624	0.00	0.0437	0.0810
		High	0.0708	0.00	0.0526	0.0890
LCOM	0.00	Low	0.0020	0.00	0.0012	0.0028
		Med	0.0019	0.00	0.0012	0.0027
		High	0.0017	0.00	0.0010	0.0024
Fan-in	0.00	Low	0.0131	0.38	-0.0165	0.0428
		Med	0.0326	0.02	0.0051	0.0600
		High	0.0891	0.00	0.0648	0.1134
Fan-out	0.22	Low	NA	NA	NA	NA
		Med	NA	NA	NA	NA
		High	NA	NA	NA	NA

Table 24: Moderation effect of size on the relationship between individual OO metrics and Faults in Ant

	Interaction Effect (P)	LOC	Effect	P	LLCI	ULCI
RFC	0.00	Low	0.0070	0.00	0.0035	0.0106
		Med	0.0077	0.00	0.0043	0.0112
		High	0.0099	0.00	0.0067	0.0131
WMC	0.00	Low	0.0021	0.67	-0.0075	0.0116
		Med	0.0040	0.39	-0.0052	0.0132
		High	0.0098	0.02	-0.0059	0.0182
CBO	0.00	Low	-0.0017	0.26	-0.0048	0.0013
		Med	-0.0007	0.62	-0.0036	0.0021
		High	0.0023	0.08	-0.0002	0.0048
LCOM	0.01	Low	0.0000	0.90	-0.0006	0.0005
		Med	0.0000	0.99	-0.0005	0.0005
		High	0.0001	0.62	-0.0003	0.0006
Fan-in	0.00	Low	-0.0023	0.14	-0.0054	0.0007
		Med	-0.0014	0.34	-0.0043	0.0015
		High	0.0013	0.30	-0.0012	0.0039
Fan-out	0.00	Low	0.0104	0.21	-0.0059	0.0268
		Med	0.0162	0.04	0.0007	0.0317
		High	0.0333	0.00	0.0195	0.0471

Table 25: Moderation effect of size on the relationship between individual OO metrics and Faults in Ivy

	Interaction Effect (P)	LOC	Effect	P	LLCI	ULCI
RFC	0.65	Low	NA	NA	NA	NA
		Med	NA	NA	NA	NA
		High	NA	NA	NA	NA
WMC	0.49	Low	NA	NA	NA	NA
		Med	NA	NA	NA	NA
		High	NA	NA	NA	NA
CBO	0.42	Low	NA	NA	NA	NA
		Med	NA	NA	NA	NA
		High	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCOM	0.31	Low	NA	NA	NA	NA
		Med	NA	NA	NA	NA
		High	NA	NA	NA	NA
Fan-in	0.08	Low	NA	NA	NA	NA
		Med	NA	NA	NA	NA
		High	NA	NA	NA	NA
Fan-out	0.33	Low	NA	NA	NA	NA
		Med	NA	NA	NA	NA
		High	NA	NA	NA	NA

Table 26: Moderation effect of size on the relationship between individual OO metrics and Faults in jEdit

	Interaction Effect (P)	LOC	Effect	P	LLCI	ULCI
RFC	0.25	Low	NA	NA	NA	NA
		Med	NA	NA	NA	NA
		High	NA	NA	NA	NA
WMC	0.00	Low	0.0029	0.00	0.0011	0.0047
		Med	0.0029	0.00	0.0011	0.0046
		High	0.0028	0.00	0.0010	0.0045
CBO	0.34	Low	NA	NA	NA	NA
		Med	NA	NA	NA	NA
		High	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCOM	0.00	Low	0.0000	0.02	0.0000	0.0001
		Med	0.0000	0.02	0.0000	0.0001
		High	0.0000	0.02	0.0000	0.0001
Fan-in	0.92	Low	NA	NA	NA	NA
		Med	NA	NA	NA	NA
		High	NA	NA	NA	NA
Fan-out	0.12	Low	NA	NA	NA	NA
		Med	NA	NA	NA	NA
		High	NA	NA	NA	NA

Table 27: Moderation effect of size on the relationship between individual OO metrics and Faults in Lucene 2.2

	Interaction Effect (P)	LOC	Effect	P	LLCI	ULCI
RFC	0.00	Low	0.0794	0.00	0.0665	0.0923
		Med	0.0798	0.00	0.0669	0.0926
		High	0.0810	0.00	0.0683	0.0937
WMC	0.01	Low	0.1598	0.00	0.1271	0.1925
		Med	0.1605	0.00	0.1279	0.1930
		High	0.1629	0.00	0.1308	0.1950
CBO	0.00	Low	0.0616	0.00	0.0403	0.0830
		Med	0.0680	0.00	0.0474	0.0885
		High	0.0897	0.00	0.0701	0.1093
LCOM	0.01	Low	0.0050	0.00	0.0037	0.0063
		Med	0.0050	0.00	0.0036	0.0063
		High	0.0049	0.00	0.0036	0.0061
Fan-in	0.00	Low	0.0168	0.21	-0.0092	0.0428
		Med	0.0343	0.00	0.0106	0.0580
		High	0.0946	0.00	0.0721	0.1171
Fan-out	0.00	Low	0.1354	0.00	0.0858	0.1851
		Med	0.1409	0.00	0.0922	0.1897
		High	0.1598	0.00	0.1130	0.2067

Table 28: Moderation effect of size on the relationship between individual OO metrics and Faults in Log4j

	Interaction Effect (P)	LOC	Effect	P	LLCI	ULCI
RFC	0.01	Low	-0.0019	0.87	-0.0250	0.0212
		Med	-0.0029	0.80	-0.0256	0.0198
		High	-0.0048	0.66	-0.0268	0.0172
WMC	0.00	Low	0.0561	0.01	0.0131	0.0991
		Med	0.0516	0.02	0.0098	0.0934
		High	0.0433	0.03	0.0033	0.0832
CBO	0.00	Low	0.0519	0.00	0.0254	0.0784
		Med	0.0452	0.00	0.0202	0.0703
		High	0.0330	0.01	0.0092	0.0569
LCOM	0.02	Low	0.0033	0.09	-0.0006	0.0072
		Med	0.0031	0.10	-0.0006	0.0069
		High	0.0028	0.12	-0.0007	0.0062
Fan-in	0.00	Low	0.0559	0.00	0.0270	0.0848
		Med	0.0465	0.00	0.0199	0.0731
		High	0.0293	0.02	0.0050	0.0536
Fan-out	0.00	Low	0.0591	0.17	-0.0252	0.1434
		Med	0.0514	0.22	-0.030600	0.1334
		High	0.0373	0.35	-0.0410	0.1156

Table 29: Moderation effect of size on the relationship between individual OO metrics and Faults in Prop

	Interaction Effect (P)	LOC	Effect	P	LLCI	ULCI
RFC	0.68	Low	NA	NA	NA	NA
		Med	NA	NA	NA	NA
		High	NA	NA	NA	NA
WMC	.95	Low	NA	NA	NA	NA
		Med	NA	NA	NA	NA
		High	NA	NA	NA	NA
CBO	0.90	Low	NA	NA	NA	NA
		Med	NA	NA	NA	NA
		High	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCOM	0.94	Low	NA	NA	NA	NA
		Med	NA	NA	NA	NA
		High	NA	NA	NA	NA
Fan-in	0.62	Low	NA	NA	NA	NA
		Med	NA	NA	NA	NA
		High	NA	NA	NA	NA
Fan-out	0.74	Low	NA	NA	NA	NA
		Med	NA	NA	NA	NA
		High	NA	NA	NA	NA

Table 30: Moderation effect of size on the relationship between individual OO metrics and Faults in Synapse

	Interaction Effect (P)	LOC	Effect	P	LLCI	ULCI
RFC	0.19	Low	NA	NA	NA	NA
		Med	NA	NA	NA	NA
		High	NA	NA	NA	NA
WMC	0.39	Low	NA	NA	NA	NA
		Med	NA	NA	NA	NA
		High	NA	NA	NA	NA
CBO	0.00	Low	0.0065	0.28	-0.0053	0.0183
		Med	0.0142	0.01	0.0035	0.0250
		High	0.0342	0.00	0.0203	0.0481
LCOM	0.45	Low	NA	NA	NA	NA
		Med	NA	NA	NA	NA
		High	NA	NA	NA	NA
Fan-in	0.13	Low	NA	NA	NA	NA
		Med	NA	NA	NA	NA
		High	NA	NA	NA	NA
Fan-out	0.00	Low	0.0105	0.46	-0.0175	0.0386
		Med	0.0206	0.11	-0.0044	0.0457
		High	0.0468	0.00	0.0240	0.0696

Table 31: Moderation effect of size on the relationship between individual OO metrics and Faults in Tomcat

	Interaction Effect (P)	LOC	Effect	P	LLCI	ULCI
RFC	0.99	Low	NA	NA	NA	NA
		Med	NA	NA	NA	NA
		High	NA	NA	NA	NA
WMC	0.18	Low	NA	NA	NA	NA
		Med	NA	NA	NA	NA
		High	NA	NA	NA	NA
CBO	0.26	Low	NA	NA	NA	NA
		Med	NA	NA	NA	NA
		High	NA	NA	NA	NA
LCOM	0.54	Low	NA	NA	NA	NA
		Med	NA	NA	NA	NA
		High	NA	NA	NA	NA
Fan-in	0.24	Low	NA	NA	NA	NA
		Med	NA	NA	NA	NA
		High	NA	NA	NA	NA
Fan-out	NA	Low	NA	NA	NA	NA
		Med	NA	NA	NA	NA
		High	NA	NA	NA	NA

Table 32: Moderation effect of size on the relationship between individual OO metrics and Faults in Velocity

	Interaction Effect (P)	LOC	Effect	P	LLCI	ULCI
RFC	0.35	Low	NA	NA	NA	NA
		Med	NA	NA	NA	NA
		High	NA	NA	NA	NA
WMC	0.66	Low	NA	NA	NA	NA
		Med	NA	NA	NA	NA
		High	NA	NA	NA	NA
CBO	0.02	Low	0.0186	0.03	0.0013	0.0359
		Med	0.0192	0.03	0.0021	0.0364
		High	0.0214	0.01	0.0048	0.0380
LCOM	0.23	Low	NA	NA	NA	NA
		Med	NA	NA	NA	NA
		High	NA	NA	NA	NA
Fan-in	0.02	Low	-0.0037	0.72	-0.0236	0.0163
		Med	-0.0028	0.78	-0.0226	0.0169
		High	0.0000	1.00	-0.0192	0.0193
Fan-out	0.39	Low	NA	NA	NA	NA
		Med	NA	NA	NA	NA
		High	NA	NA	NA	NA

Table 33: Moderation effect of size on the relationship between individual OO metrics and Faults in Xalan

	Interaction Effect (P)	LOC	Effect	P	LLCI	ULCI
RFC	0.32	Low	NA	NA	NA	NA
		Med	NA	NA	NA	NA
		High	NA	NA	NA	NA
WMC	0.02	Low	0.0011	0.66	0.0037	0.0058
		Med	0.0015	0.50	-0.0029	0.0060
		High	0.0036	0.03	0.0003	0.0069
CBO	0.01	Low	0.0043	0.01	0.0012	0.0075
		Med	0.0049	0.00	0.0019	0.0078
		High	0.0070	0.00	0.0046	0.0095
LCOM	0.24	Low	NA	NA	NA	NA
		Med	NA	NA	NA	NA
		High	NA	NA	NA	NA
Fan-in	0.06	Low	0.0033	0.08	-0.0004	0.0070
		Med	0.0038	0.03	0.0005	0.0072
		High	0.0062	0.00	0.0031	0.0092
Fan-out	0.00	Low	0.0064	0.06	-0.0004	0.0132
		Med	0.0076	0.02	0.0013	0.0139
		High	0.0125	0.00	0.0075	0.0175

Table 34: Moderation effect of size on the relationship between individual OO metrics and Faults in Apache Xerces

	Interaction Effect (P)	LOC	Effect	P	LLCI	ULCI
RFC	0.48	Low	NA	NA	NA	NA
		Med	NA	NA	NA	NA
		High	NA	NA	NA	NA
WMC	0.00	Low	0.1186	0.00	0.0756	0.1616
		Med	0.1159	0.00	0.0732	0.1585
		High	0.0941	0.00	0.0535	0.1346
CBO	0.01	Low	0.1554	0.00	0.1105	0.2004
		Med	0.1576	0.00	0.1132	0.2020
		High	0.1751	0.00	0.1332	0.2170
LCOM	0.00	Low	0.0084	0.00	0.0060	0.0107
		Med	0.0082	0.00	0.0059	0.0105
		High	0.0068	0.00	0.0046	0.0089
Fan-in	0.06	Low	0.1100	0.00	0.0524	0.1676
		Med	0.1070	0.00	0.0509	0.1676
		High	0.0836	0.00	0.0338	0.1335
Fan-out	0.33	Low	NA	NA	NA	NA
		Med	NA	NA	NA	NA
		High	NA	NA	NA	NA

6 Moderation analysis results for aggregated data

Results of the moderation analysis in both datasets (DAMB and JURE) are shown in Table 35.

7 Simple slopes analysis plots

This section presents simple slopes analysis plots to illustrate the moderation effect of class size on the relationships between all OO metrics and faults. We only present metrics with significant moderation effects.

Figure 18: Moderation effect of size on the relationship between RFC and faults in JDT

Table 35: Moderation effect of size on the relationship between individual OO metrics and Faults for DAMB Dataset and JURE Dataset

Lucene 2.4										POI		
Metric	Interaction (moderation effect)	LOC	Effect	<i>p</i>	BootLLCI	BootULCI	Interaction (moderation effect)	Effect	<i>p</i>	BootLLCI	BootULCI	
RFC	0.00	Low	0.0047	0.00	0.0041	0.0052	0.00	0.0085	0.0000	0.0065	0.0106	
		Med	0.0047	0.00	0.0041	0.0052		0.0083	0.0000	0.0063	0.0104	
		High	0.0046	0.00	0.0041	0.0051		0.0076	0.0000	0.0057	0.0096	
WMC	0.00	Low	0.0043	0.00	0.0033	0.0054	0.00	0.0143	0.0000	0.0093	0.0193	
		Med	0.0043	0.00	0.0032	0.0053		0.0138	0.0000	0.0089	0.0188	
		High	0.0041	0.00	0.0031	0.0052		0.0123	0.0000	0.0075	0.0170	
CBO	0.00	Low	0.0116	0.0000	0.0097	0.0135	0.00	0.0106	0.0000	0.0068	0.0144	
		Med	0.0118	0.00	0.0099	0.0137		0.0103	0.0000	0.0066	0.014	
		High	0.0125	0.00	0.0107	0.0144		0.0094	0.0000	0.006	0.0128	
LCOM	0.00	Low	0.0002	0.00	0.0001	0.0002	0.00	0.0001	0.3069	-0.0001	0.0002	
		Med	0.0002	0.00	0.0001	0.0002		0.0001	0.3290	-0.0001	0.0002	
		High	0.0002	0.00	0.0001	0.0002		0.0001	0.8093	-0.0001	0.0002	
Fan-in	0.00	Low	0.0056	0.00	0.0033	0.0078	0.01	0.0061	0.0042	0.0019	0.0103	
		Med	0.0058	0.00	0.0036	0.0080		0.0058	0.0050	0.0017	0.0980	
		High	0.0066	0.00	0.0044	0.0087		0.0047	0.0122	0.001	0.0084	
Fan-out	0.00	Low	0.0405	0.00	0.0363	0.0447	0.91	NA	NA	NA	NA	
		Med	0.0407	0.00	0.0366	0.0449		NA	NA	NA	NA	
		High	0.0415	0.00	0.0375	0.0456		NA	NA	NA	NA	

Figure 19: Moderation effect of size on the relationship between WMC and faults in JDT

Figure 20: Moderation effect of size on the relationship between Fan-in and faults in JDT

Figure 21: Moderation effect of size on the relationship between Fan-out and faults in JDT

Figure 22: Moderation effect of size on the relationship between RFC and faults in Mylyn

Figure 23: Moderation effect of size on the relationship between WMC and faults in Mylyn

Figure 24: Moderation effect of size on the relationship between CBO and faults in Mylyn

Figure 25: Moderation effect of size on the relationship between LCOM and faults in Mylyn

Figure 26: Moderation effect of size on the relationship between Fan-in and faults in Mylyn

Figure 27: Moderation effect of size on the relationship between Fan-out and faults in Mylyn

Figure 28: Moderation effect of size on the relationship between LCOM and faults in PDE

Figure 29: Moderation effect of size on the relationship between RFC and faults in Equinox

Figure 30: Moderation effect of size on the relationship between WMC and faults in Equinox

Figure 31: Moderation effect of size on the relationship between CBO and faults in Equinox

Figure 32: Moderation effect of size on the relationship between LCOM and faults in Equinox

Figure 33: Moderation effect of size on the relationship between Fan-in and faults in Equinox

Figure 34: Moderation effect of size on the relationship between RFC and faults in Lucene (2.4)

Figure 35: Moderation effect of size on the relationship between WMC and faults in Lucene (2.4)

Figure 36: Moderation effect of size on the relationship between CBO and faults in Lucene (2.4)

Figure 37: Moderation effect of size on the relationship between LCOM and faults in Lucene (2.4)

Figure 38: Moderation effect of size on the relationship between Fan-in and faults in Lucene (2.4)

Figure 39: Moderation effect of size on the relationship between Fan-out and faults in Lucene (2.4)

Figure 40: Moderation effect of size on the relationship between RFC and faults in Ant

Figure 41: Moderation effect of size on the relationship between WMC and faults in Ant

Figure 42: Moderation effect of size on the relationship between CBO and faults in Ant

Figure 43: Moderation effect of size on the relationship between lcom and faults in Ant

Figure 44: Moderation effect of size on the relationship between Fan-in and faults in Ant

Figure 45: Moderation effect of size on the relationship between Fan-out and faults in Ant

Figure 46: Moderation effect of size on the relationship between WMC and faults in jEdit

Figure 47: Moderation effect of size on the relationship between LCOM and faults in jEdit

Figure 48: Moderation effect of size on the relationship between RFC and faults in Log4J

Figure 49: Moderation effect of size on the relationship between WMC and faults in Log4J

Figure 50: Moderation effect of size on the relationship between CBO and faults in Log4J

Figure 51: Moderation effect of size on the relationship between LCOM and faults in Log4J

Figure 52: Moderation effect of size on the relationship between Fan-in and faults in Log4J

Figure 53: Moderation effect of size on the relationship between Fan-out and faults in Log4J

Figure 54: Moderation effect of size on the relationship between RFC and faults in Lucene (2.2)

Figure 55: Moderation effect of size on the relationship between WMC and faults in Lucene (2.2)

Figure 56: Moderation effect of size on the relationship between CBO and faults in Lucene (2.2)

Figure 57: Moderation effect of size on the relationship between LCOM and faults in Lucene (2.2)

Figure 58: Moderation effect of size on the relationship between Fan-in and faults in Lucene (2.2)

Figure 59: Moderation effect of size on the relationship between Fan-out and faults in Lucene (2.2)

Figure 60: Moderation effect of size on the relationship between WMC and faults in POI

Figure 61: Moderation effect of size on the relationship between CBO and faults in POI

Figure 62: Moderation effect of size on the relationship between LCOM and faults in POI

Figure 63: Moderation effect of size on the relationship between Fan-in and faults in POI

Figure 64: Moderation effect of size on the relationship between Fan-out and faults in POI

Figure 65: Moderation effect of size on the relationship between CBO and faults in Synapse

Figure 66: Moderation effect of size on the relationship between Fan-out and faults in Synapse

Figure 67: Moderation effect of size on the relationship between CBO and faults in Velocity

Figure 68: Moderation effect of size on the relationship between Fan-in and faults in Velocity

Figure 69: Moderation effect of size on the relationship between WMC and faults in Xalan

Figure 70: Moderation effect of size on the relationship between CBO and faults in Xalan

Figure 71: Moderation effect of size on the relationship between Fan-out and faults in Xalan

Figure 72: Moderation effect of size on the relationship between WMC and faults in Xerces

Figure 73: Moderation effect of size on the relationship between LCOM and faults in Xerces